

DESTRUCTION OF THE LIPASE IN THE OIL SEEDS AS THE MOLDS GROW ON THEM

BY C. V. RAMAKRISHNAN AND B. N. BANERJEE

The synthetic and hydrolytic activities of lipases extracted from good castor and groundnut seeds, the moldy oil seeds and the molds grown on those oil seeds were studied and the results recorded.

Ramakrishnan and Nevgi (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1951, **33B**, 260) while investigating the different oil seeds for their lipase activity have found that lipase extracted from castor and groundnut seeds show better activity. While investigating the oil seeds for their lipolytic activity, Ramakrishnan and Banerjee ("Mold Lipases", 1951, *Science*, in press) have found that molds grow on oil seeds due to improper storage and the different strains like *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium chrysogenum* etc., isolated from the molds grown on these oil seeds, show better lipolytic activity than the oil seeds. Hence, an investigation was carried out to study how far the activity of the lipase in the oil seeds was affected by the mold growth.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Lipase.—In one experiment, the lipase was extracted from good variety of castor (*Ricinus communis*) and groundnut (*Arachis hypogea*) seeds according to Longnecker and Haly's method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 2019). In another experiment, the molds were allowed to grow on the castor and groundnut seeds kept in two desiccators adjusting the moisture content and regulating the flow of air. The molds grown on the oil seeds were subcultured in Czapek agar medium in petri dishes and pure cultures prepared. Staining method used by Bayliss, Glick and Siem (*J. Bact.*, 1948, **10**, 5B, 307) as well as the biological method used by Grabill and Reed (*Biochem. Bull.*, 1915, **4**, 30) were used to detect the lipolytic molds from the pure cultures obtained. The highly lipolytic strains *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus*, isolated from castor source, and *Penicillium chrysogenum* and *Aspergillus oryzae*, isolated from groundnut source, were grown in one litre capacity conical flasks containing 200 c.c. groundnut cake medium which contained 10% freshly prepared groundnut oil and 20% oil-free groundnut cake and autoclaved for 15 minutes under 15 lbs. pressure, inoculated with mold and incubated at 37°, and after a week the mats formed were removed, washed well with sterilised water and extracted with low boiling petroleum ether to remove the fatty materials from the mat. They were completely dried at room temperature to remove the solvent, powdered well, sieved through a 60 mesh sieve, and the powder obtained was used for the experiment.

In the third experiment, the molds grown on the seeds were removed, the skins peeled off and the meal was completely washed with sterilised water to remove the traces of molds present, and the lipase prepared from it according to Longnecker and Haly's method (*loc. cit.*).

The activities of these lipases were studied by carrying out the hydrolysis of freshly prepared groundnut oil by these lipases using disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer.

Each set of the experiments consisted of 1 c.c. of groundnut oil, 5 c.c. of water, 2 c.c. of buffer mixture of varying p_H , 0.1 g. of lipase and a few drops of toluene in a conical flask, shaken well and kept in the incubator at 37° for 24 hours. Always a blank accompanied each sample. After the period of incubation, the contents of the flask was taken out, 25 c.c. of neutral alcohol added, warmed for some time and titrated against $N/10$ -NaOH. Necessary precautions were taken to take readings under sterile conditions. The activity of the lipase is expressed in terms of the difference in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH between the sample and the blank. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Buffer: Disodium phosphate-citric acid, Oil: Groundnut oil, (f.f. as, 0.05).

Difference in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH between the sample and the blank in case of lipase from

p_H	Good before mold growth.	castor seed after mold growth.	<i>A. niger</i> isolated from source.	<i>A. flavus</i> from castor.	Good groundnut seed before mold growth.	after mold growth.	<i>A. Oryzae</i> from groundnut source.	<i>P. crysogtum</i>
3.2	7.0	0.8	8.3	7.5	5.0	0.5	5.6	4.9
3.6	7.8	1.1	8.0	8.1	5.3	1.0	8.9	7.3
4.8	13.0	2.6	9.2	8.9	7.2	1.2	10.9	10.5
5.2	8.9	2.0	10.8	9.2	11.8	1.8	12.3	11.8
5.7	6.9	1.7	15.4	11.8	6.8	1.0	15.5	13.1
6.2	5.8	1.2	19.5	14.3	4.2	0.7	18.8	15.9
7.2	4.7	0.5	22.6	10.9	3.3	0.5	5.7	9.8
7.4	3.9	—	17.3	9.2	2.7	—	2.8	5.4

TABLE II

Difference in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH between the sample and the blank in case of

Name of the lipase and p_H of the buffer used.	Fresh castor oil.	Castor oil extracted from the moldy seed.	Highly rancid castor oil.	Fresh groundnut oil.	Groundnut oil extracted from moldy seed.	Highly rancid groundnut oil.
	f.f.a. 0.08%.	f.f.a. 0.87%.	f.f.a. 3.5%.	f.f.a. 0.05%.	f.f.a. 0.54%.	f.f.a. 3.1%.
Lipase from good castor seed (p_H 4.8)	13.8	8.2	1.1	13.0	8.0	0.2
Lipase from castor seed after mold growth (p_H 4.8)	2.6	1.6	0.2	2.6	1.2	0.1
Lipase from <i>A. niger</i> isolated from castor source (p_H 7.2)	23.1	19.2	2.3	22.6	18.5	0.8
Lipase from good groundnut seed (p_H 5.2)	12.8	10.3	0.8	11.8	9.8	0.2
Lipase from groundnut after mold growth (p_H 5.2)	2.3	1.1	0.2	1.8	0.7	0.1
<i>A. oryzae</i> isolated from groundnut source (p_H 6.2)	19.1	16.5	1.8	18.8	13.9	0.5

TABLE III

Buffer : Disodium phosphate-citric acid. Oil: Groundnut oil (f.f.a., 0.05%).

Difference in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH between the sample and the blank for lipase from

Time.	Good castor seed.	Moldy castor seed.	<i>A. niger</i> from castor source.	Good groundnut.	Moldy groundnut.	<i>A. Oryzae</i> from groundnut source.
	* p_H 4.8.	* p_H 4.8.	* p_H 7.2.	* p_H 5.2	* p_H 5.2	* p_H 6.2.
7 days	13.0	2.6	22.6	11.8	1.8	18.8
10	13.0	2.0	24.1	11.7	1.3	19.5
20	12.8	1.2	24.1	11.5	0.9	19.6
30	11.8	0.8	24.1	11.0	0.4	19.4
60	11.2	0.3	22.8	10.7	0.4	18.2

* p_H of the buffer used.

TABLE IV

Solvent : Ethyl ether.

Percentage synthesis of butyl oleate on

Lipase. from	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.	7th day.
Good castor seed	16.5	29.7	40.2	50.7	52.5	62.7	60.3
Moldy castor seed	2.6	4.8	6.4	7.5	8.1	9.5	7.8
<i>A. niger</i> isolated from castor source	17.2	28.9	41.6	49.8	52.3	65.8	61.3
Good groundnut	15.9	32.8	49.5	56.2	61.8	58.5	—
Moldy groundnut	2.3	5.1	7.0	8.1	8.1	8.3	—
<i>A. oryzae</i> isolated from groundnut source	15.4	30.7	45.8	52.3	60.8	63.4	60.9

From Table I it can be seen that the optimum p_H for the activity of the lipase extracted from good as well as moldy oil seed is the same even though the activity has decreased in the second case. The lipase extracted from the molds grown on the oil seeds show high activity at optimum p_H of 6.2 to 7.2 depending upon the mold from which it is extracted.

The hydrolysis of the oils extracted from the good oil seed, moldy oil seed as well as highly rancid oils was studied using these lipases and disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer. Buffer mixture of p_H 4.8 was used in the case of lipase from good and moldy castor seeds ; buffer mixture of p_H 5.2 in the case of lipase from good and moldy groundnut seed ; buffer mixture of p_H 7.2 and 6.2 respectively in cases of lipases from *A. niger* and *A. oryzae* respectively. The results are given in Table II.

From Table II it can be seen that the hydrolysis is high in fresh oil in all cases and decreases in the order : fresh oil, oil from the moldy seed and highly rancid oil. The free fatty acid of the oil increases in the order : fresh oil, moldy oil and rancid oil. Highly rancid oil is the least hydrolysed by all lipases and the lipase activity in the oil seed is the least in the case of the moldy oil seed.

The molds were allowed to grow on oil seeds and at different intervals of time ; the lipase was extracted from the moldy oil seeds as well as certain strains isolated from the

molds grown on them. The activities of these lipases were found out by studying the hydrolysis of groundnut oil using these lipases and disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer. The results are shown in Table III.

From Table III it can be seen that in the case of stored oil seed, the activity of the lipase slowly decreases. As the molds grow on the oil seeds, the activity of the lipase extracted from the molds increases with ageing up to a certain limit and then decreases, whereas the activity of the lipase from the moldy oil seeds decreases as the molds grow on them. This proves that the lipase in the oil seeds is destroyed as the molds grow on them.

Finally, the synthesis of butyl oleate was carried out using these lipases to see how far the synthetic activity of the lipase in the oil seeds was affected by the molds grown on them.

The acetone-dried samples of these lipases were prepared according to Ramakrishnan and Nevgi's method (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1950, 19, Part III, 34) and used for the experiment.

In different conical flasks, equimolecular quantities (0.054 g. mol.) of butyl alcohol [b.p. 117°; *d*, 0.809 g./c.c., M.W., 74.1] and oleic acid [b. p. 286°; *d*, 0.895 g./c.c. M. W., 282.4] were added. The lipase (1 g.) and ether solvent (10 c.c.) were added to each flask, shaken well and kept in the incubator at 37° after corking well. At different intervals of time, 1 c.c. from each flask was taken, 25 c.c. of neutral alcohol added, warmed for some time and titrated against *N*/10 sodium hydroxide. Always a blank accompanied each sample. The difference between the sample and the blank was calculated in terms of c.c. of *N*/10-NaOH. From this the percentage synthesis was calculated. The results are shown in Table IV.

From Table IV it can be seen that the synthetic activity of the lipase extracted from the oil seeds also decreases as the molds grow on the oil seeds, whereas the synthetic activity of the lipase extracted from the molds grown on the oil seeds is more than that extracted from the oil seeds.

From the above, it can be observed that the activity of the lipase in the oil seeds decreases as the molds grow on them, whereas the activity of the lipase extracted from the molds grown on the oil seeds is more than that extracted from good oil seeds.

The authors' thanks are due to the Indian Council of Medical Research for having awarded a Research Fellowship to one of us (C. V. R.) to carry out this investigation.